

REPORT ON STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF AGRIBUSINESS PROFITABILITY

ANALYSIS OF AMADEUS DATA BETWEEN 2012 & 2017

PROJECT
REPORT
D5.4

VALUMICS - UNDERSTANDING FOOD VALUE
CHAINS AND NETWORK DYNAMICS

MAY 2020

Food Systems Dynamics

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ABOUT

VALUMICS stands for value chain dynamics and is a research project funded by the EU H2020 programme. VALUMICS will enable decision makers to evaluate policy impact on food value chains

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Food industry profitability and its determinants is an important area for study, with previous research investigating the relative importance of firm and industry level effects. This study employs Hierarchical Linear Modelling (HLM) to understand the determinants of food industry profitability, drawing on firm financial data for the years 2012 to 2017 from the AMADEUS database (n = 8,645 records). Data relate to EU countries. Return on Assets (ROA) is the dependent variable employed with independent variables considered relating to firm (level 1) and industry (level 2) effects. The key findings of the analysis are:

- Market concentration has a positive effect on return on assets;
- Sales growth has a positive effect on return on assets;
- Market share has a positive effect on return on assets;
- Firm age has a negative effect on return on assets;
- Firm size has a positive effect on return on assets;
- Short-term financial risk (debt) has negative effect on return on assets;
- Market concentration positively moderates the relationship between market share and return on assets;
- Industry sales growth positively moderates the relationship between market share and return on assets.

For companies seeking to improve their return on assets, the three main strategies suggested from the analysis relate to: *relative size and market power* (increasing market share and market concentration to achieve greater profitability), *reducing short-term debts risks* to improve their long-term profitability and focusing on *growing market segments*.

1. INTRODUCTION

The H2020 VALUMICS project aims to provide decision makers throughout food value chains with a comprehensive suite of approaches and tools that will enable them to evaluate the impact of strategic and operational policies to enhance the resilience, integrity and sustainability of food value chains for European countries.

WP5 aims to investigate upstream and downstream food value chain agents/actors (firms/companies) across the chain, building on previous work from WP2 on system dynamics, WP3 on food policy mapping and system governance, and WP4 on food system case study groundwork. Specifically, WP5 adopts a multidimensional approach and empirical analysis to account for economic aspects of food chains.

This document (D5.4) is the deliverable for Task 5.6, which focuses on understanding the determinants of EU agri-food industry profitability using regression models and accounting data, provided by the Bureau van Dijk's AMADEUS database, with records relating to firms in the food manufacturing/processing sector selected.

The next section discusses the theoretical basis for the research and presents a review of the existing literature.

1.1 BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE LITERATURE ON FIRM PROFITABILITY

Firm profitability has been a subject of interest for a long time, with numerous studies seeking to explain variations in the fortunes of businesses (Roper, 1999; Zouaghi *et al.*, 2017). Classical economic models of perfect competition assume that profits above or below “normal” returns will not persist, as other firms can enter and exit the market, bidding up or down economic returns until they reach an equilibrium (Carlton and Perloff, 2005). In practice, however, variations in firm profitability persist within and across industries and explaining these patterns is an important theoretical and empirical research topic. Explanations of variations in firm profitability broadly fall into “industry effects” and “firm level effects”. The former is associated with the “structure-conduct-performance” framework that informs industrial economics theory and the pioneering work of Joe Bain (1956; 1968), which in turn influenced the work of Porter (1980) and his “five forces” model. Accordingly, variations in firm performance stem from the characteristics of the industry to which they belong. In particular, average

rates of return will be higher in industries characterised by a high level of concentration and high barriers to entry (Caves and Porter, 1977; Waring, 1996; Slater and Olson, 2002). However, industry effects alone cannot explain variations in firm profitability, leading to a consideration of differences in firms' tangible and intangible resources for explaining variations in enterprise profitability (Barney, 1991). These differences (the "firm level effects") form the basis of the Resource Based View (RBV) theory, which argues that firms with distinctive and superior (tangible and intangible) resources and capabilities perform better (Barney, 2001).

Following the work of Barney (1991), RBV assumes that to achieve superior profitability, distinctive and superior (valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable) resources and capabilities, compared to competitors, are required. In this framework, resources are "bundles of tangible and intangible assets, including firm's management skills, its organizational processes and routines, and the information and knowledge it controls that can be used by firms to help choose and implement strategies" (Barney *et al.*, 2011, p. 1300). Tangible resources include financial and physical factors of production while intangible resources include know-how and reputation (Goddard *et al.*, 2006). While both are significant, empirical evidence suggests that 'firm effects' are more important than 'industry effects' when explaining variations in firm profitability (McGahan and Porter, 1997; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003).

1.2 FIRM PROFITABILITY IN THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR

Several studies investigate variations in enterprise profitability in the agri-food industry, considering the existence of 'industry' and 'firm level' effects (Szymanski *et al.*, 2007; Hirsch and Gschwandtner, 2013; Schiefer *et al.*, 2013; Hirsch *et al.*, 2014; Hirsch and Schiefer, 2016; Blažková and Dvouletý, 2018). Generally, these studies highlight that average rates of return in the food industries are modest, particularly when compared to other sectors of the economy (Toming, 2007).

Focusing on analysis at the EU level or its Member States, Table 1 summarises previous empirical investigations. For example, considering the Polish food industry, Szymanski *et al.* (2007) found that firm effects (e.g., ownership and location) were the most important determinants of profitability. Comparative analysis across countries (e.g., Hirsch and Gschwandtner (2013); Hirsch and Hartmann (2014); Hirsch *et al.* (2014); Hirsch and Schiefer (2016), using AMADEUS data, emphasise several firm

level factors that explain variations in profitability across food industry enterprises. Specifically, these studies found evidence that for the EU food industry, the most important determinants of variations in business profitability are firm size, market share, industry growth, firm age, advertising, R&D (intensity), patents (innovation activity), firm financial risk, industry concentration, and territorial factors (such as level of education and unemployment in the region).

Table 1 Selected recent agribusiness firm profitability studies using EU AMADEUS data

No	Publication	Geography	Method	Findings	Note	DV	IV
1	Hirsch and Gschwandtner (2013)	Belgium, France, Italy, Spain and the UK	Arellano-Bond dynamic panel models (GMM – general method of moments)	Degree of profit in food is lower than manufacturing due to competition among food processors and high retailer concentration. Firm size (+) Firm age, risk and R&D intensity (-)	Applied to general food industry sector; The use ROA as DV (despite criticism of biased via profit-smoothing and cross-subsidisation) was due to data availability and to assure comparability to the previous literature	Abnormal profit via AR (1) (auto-regressive process of order one)	<u>Firm variables:</u> Firm sales/industry sales; Firm age; Total assets (TA); Growth rate of TA; Gearing ratio; 1/Current ratio; <u>Industry variables:</u> Herfindahl-Hirschman Index; Number of firms in industry; Growth rate of the number firms in the industry; Share of R%D expenditure in industry value added; Five firms concentration ratio of the retail sector
2	Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Belgium, France, Italy, Spain, UK (because it has complete ROA data; and account for 56% of the enterprises)	Hierarchical Linear Model (HLM)	Firm effects are far more important than industry structure.	Total sample use: 5,494 enterprises with mean ROA of 4.9%. Insignificant coef. of R&D is a result of the large share of small and	Return on Assets (ROA)	<u>Firm variables:</u> <i>MS</i> , Firm sales/industry sales; <i>Age</i> , firm age; <i>Ln TA</i> (natural logarithm of total assets); <i>Gr.TA</i> , growth rate of total assets; <i>Gear</i> , gearing ratio;

		and 54% of turnover on the EU 27 food industry)		Firm size and industry concentration (+) Firm risk, age and industry growth (-)	rather insignificant innovations (Hoban, 1998)		1/Curr, 1/current ratio <u>Industry variables:</u> HHI, Herfindahl-Hirschman Index; NF, number of firms in industry adjusted by industry sales; Gr.NF, Growth rate of NF; R&D, share of R&D expenditure in industry value added; CR5, Five-firm concentration ratio of the food retail sector
3	Hirsch and Hartmann (2014)	Belgium, France, Italy, Spain and the UK (chosen by means of sample sizes and by total dairy processing industry turnover- 51.6% of total EU-27 in 2007)	Autoregressive model (AR) and dynamic panel (Arellano-Bond)	20% of firms (i.e. cooperatives) are not primarily profit oriented. High level of competition as profit is rather low Short- as well long-run profit is driven by firm and industry characteristics	Applied to the European dairy processing industry only. The industry is characterized by considerable policy intervention and a high share of cooperatives (20%) relative to other sectors.	Abnormal profit (execution excluding cooperatives, as the dynamic panel model is based on the assumption of profit maximization which does not hold for cooperatives)	<u>Firm variables:</u> MS= firm sales/industry sales; Age= firm age; Ln TA= natural algorithm of total assets; Gr.TA= growth rate of total assets; Gear= gearing ratio; 1/Curr= 1/current ratio <u>Industry variables:</u> HHI= Herfindahl-Hirschman Index; NF= number of firms in industry divided by industry sales; Gr.NF= growth rate of NF; R&D= share of R&D expenditure in industry value added;

							CR5= five-firm concentration ratio of the retail sector Age was dropped from the model due to multicollinearity on long-run persistence
4	Hirsch and Schiefer (2016)	Belgium, France, Italy, Spain and the UK (54% of EU27 food industry turnover)	Hierarchical ANOVA and COV	Firm-related effects are main profit driver; Industry, year and country effects are negligible	Focus on profitability variation. Application to EU food processors (as opposed to manufacturing and food sector)	Return on Assets (ROA) is calculated for each firm and year by dividing firms' profit/loss before tax, plus interest, by total assets. (Viaene and Gellynck, 1995)	Hierarchical ANOVA descriptive model considering effects from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Year (Y) • Industry (I) • Country (C) • Y-I interactions • Y-C interactions • I-C interactions • Firm • Firm Size
5	Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Spain: (Territory Level at Local Labor Systems level)	Multilevel approach of Hierarchical Linear Modeling	The dominance of firm-specific effects (48.8%) to variance in profitability. <u>Firm effects:</u> Firm size, growth, financial risk and innovation activity are profit drivers. <u>Industry effects:</u>	Focus on firm geographical locations influence on profitability	ROA	<u>Firm level:</u> Ln TA, firm size: natural algorithm of total assets; Age, number of years since incorporation; Gr. Sales, Yearly sales growth; 1/Curr, current liabilities/current assets; Lev_debt, total debt/total assets; Innovative, dummy with value 1 if the companies perform innovation with innovation proxied by growth in tangible assets <u>Industry-level:</u>

				Concentration, size, territorial factors (regional education and unemployment) effect profitability			<p>HHI, Sum of the squared market shares of firms operating in an industry;</p> <p>Ln sales, natural logarithm of industry sales;</p> <p>Gr. NF, yearly growth rate of the number of firms in an industry.</p> <p><u>Territory-Level (LLS):</u></p> <p>Unemployment rate, LLS unemployment rate;</p> <p>Dist-port, driving minutes to nearest airport;</p> <p>Dist-tec, Driving minutes to nearest technological institute;</p> <p>Edu_level, Education level of LLS population between 30 and 39 years old. Ranging from 0 (uneducated) to 4.5 (PhD)</p> <p>Urban, Dummy with value 1 if the LLS is considered urban (>150 inhabitants/km²)</p> <p>Foreign_pop, Proportion of foreign -born population in total LLS population.</p>
6	Gschwandtner and Hirsch (2018)	US and EU	Propensity Score matching and Dynamic Panel Model (GMM)	Profit persistence in food processing is lower than in other manufacturing sectors for both US and EU – indicating high	Strong difference between US vs EU food processing industries on firms size. Low data for small size	Profit deviating from the mean	<p><u>Firm variables:</u></p> <p>Firm size, natural logarithm of total assets;</p> <p>Firm growth, yearly growth rate of total assets;</p> <p>Market share, firm sales/industry value of sales;</p>

				<p>degree of competition.</p> <p>Firms drivers of profitability are: size and financial risk</p> <p>Industry drivers of profitability are: concentration and the growth rate</p>	<p>companies in the US.</p> <p>Food processors profit persistence was only marginally affected by the economic crisis.</p> <p>US industries is impacted for the long-term financial risk</p> <p>EU sample adequately reflects the presence of family- ownership</p>		<p>Short term risk, current liabilities/current assets;</p> <p>Gearing, noncurrent liabilities/shareholder funds.</p> <p><u>Industry variables:</u></p> <p>HHI, Herfindahl Index of NAICS/NACE¹ industry;</p> <p>Industry size, sales of NAICS/NACE industry;</p> <p>Industry growth, growth rate of value of sales.</p>
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¹ NAICS and NACE are the statistical classifications of economic activities in the US and the EU, respectively.

Food industry profitability is generally lower than other sector due to high level of competition and relative fragmentation (Hirsch and Gschwandtner, 2013; Gschwandtner and Hirsch, 2018). In some countries such as Spain, the food industry is the largest branch of manufacturing by turnover and employment (Zouaghi *et al.*, 2017). However, cooperatives in the food industry, which are very important in some branches of the food industry like dairy, where they have a 20 per cent share of the EU market tend not to be very profitable and profit maximization may not be their objective (Hirsch and Hartmann, 2014).

Using Czech food manufacturing data, Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) discovered that firm age and short-run risk had a negative relationship with return of asset (ROA) but firm size had a positive relationship. Market concentration was also found to be a significant predictor of firm profitability (*ibid*). This is contrary to the US based study by Chaddad and Mondelli (2013), where market concentration was found to be positive contributor to firm profitability. Hence, overall the literature reinforces the importance of the firm level effects over the industry level effects in explaining variations in enterprise performance in the food industry (Chaddad and Mondelli, 2013).

In addition Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 summarise key variables used in the literature. A comparison with what is available in the AMADEUS database is undertaken.

Table 2 Dependent variable (DV) in the agri-food industry profitability analysis

Variable (Code in AMADEUS)	How to measure it	Note for AMADEUS database use
Return on assets (ROA)	$= \frac{\text{Earnings Before Interest and Taxes}}{\text{Total Assets}}$ [used in Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014); Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018)]	All available in € (Euro) since 2008-2017 EBIT (=Operating P/L); Total Assets; ROA using P/L before tax.

Table 3 Independent variables (IV) in the agri-food industry profitability analysis at FIRM level

Firm level characteristics		
Variables	How to measure it	Note for AMADEUS database use
Market share (MS_{ij})	$= \frac{Sales_i(\text{denotes firms})}{Sales_j(\text{denotes industry/sectors})}$ [Note: Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) – <i>positive significant</i> ; Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014) – <i>non significant</i>]	Available in € since 2008 Sales data from 10 sub food manufacturing sector.
Firm age (Age_{ij})	Number of years the firm operates in the market [Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014); Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018)– <i>negative significant</i>]	Available as date of incorporation (under the headings of Legal & account info, and Legal info)
Firm size (Size_{ij}/Ln TA)	= Ln Total Assets [All literature: positive significant]	Available in € Logarithm of Total Assets
Short-run risk (1/Curr)	$= \frac{\frac{current}{short} - term\ liabilities_{ij}}{current\ assets_{ij}}$ [All literature: negative significant]	Available as current ratio (under the heading of Financial data, and Key financials & employee)

Table 4 Independent variables (IV) in the agri-food industry profitability analysis at INDUSTRY level

Industry level characteristics		
Variable	How to measure it	Note for AMADEUS database use
Market concentration (CR4)	Four firms concentration ratio of sales in each industry for each year $\sum_{i=1}^4 MS_{ij}$	Market Share estimation based on sales data; [Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>non significant</i> ; Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) – <i>positive significant</i>]

Industry concentration Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI)	Similar to market concentration $\sum_{i=1}^N (MS_{i,j}^2)$	The sum squared Market Shares of the 50 highest-grossing firms in each industry [Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014) – <i>positive significant</i>]
Growth of sales	$= \frac{Sales_{jt} - Sales_{j,t-1}}{Sales_{j,t-1}}$	Sales data [Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) – <i>strong positive significant</i>]
Ln Sales	Natural logarithm of industry sales	Sales data [Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>negative significant</i>]
Industry growth (Gr. NF)	Yearly growth rate of the Number of Firm in an industry = growth rate of NF divided by industry sales	Firms number in an industry; Sales data [Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014); Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) - <i>negative significant</i>]
Growth of imports	Impacts of foreign competition $= \frac{Imports_{jt} - Imports_{j,t-1}}{Imports_{j,t-1}}$	Revenue related variables used [Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) – <i>strong negative significant</i>]

Other potential independent variables (IV) used in the literature were also reviewed and summarized in Table 5

Table 5 Other independent variables (IV)

Firm level characteristics		
Variable	How to measure it	Note for AMADEUS database use
Number of employees	Categorical	Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018): 1) 0-19; 2) 20-49; 3) 50-249; 4) 250 and more. Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014):

		<p>1) Micro <10 employees and total assets <€2M;</p> <p>2) Small <50 employees and total assets < €10M</p> <p>3) Medium <250 employees and total assets <€43M</p> <p>4) Large >250 employees and total assets > €43M</p>
Debt leverage (Lev_Debt)	$= \frac{\text{Total debt}_{ij}}{\text{Total assets}_{ij}}$	<p>Total debt = debtors (€);</p> <p>Total assets (€)</p> <p>[Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>negative significant to agricultural firms</i>]</p>
Innovation	<p>Dummy with value 1 if firms perform innovation with innovation proxied by growth in intangible assets</p>	<p>R&D expenses ratio to operating revenue</p> <p>[Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>positive significant to all firms and food industry</i>]</p>
Debt/Equity ratio	$= \frac{\text{Total liabilities}_{ij}}{\text{Shareholders' Equity}_{ij}}$	<p>Available in € since 2008;</p> <p>Total liabilities available as non-current liabilities;</p> <p>Shareholder equity can be estimated as:</p> <p>total assets – total liabilities</p> <p>[Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) – <i>negative significant with very low coefficient</i>]</p>
Gearing % (Gr. TA)	$= \frac{\text{non – current liabilities}_{ij} + \text{loans}_{ij}}{\text{Shareholders' Funds}_{ij}}$	<p>Non-current liabilities;</p> <p>Loans;</p> <p>shareholders' fund</p> <p>[Hirsch <i>et al.</i> (2014) – <i>weak relationship</i>]</p>

Corporate capital intensity (crpCAP)	Ratio of the net value of property plant and equipment to net sales for each corporation in each year	Tangible assets and sales data [Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>negative significant</i>]
Corporate resource availability (crpRES)	Ratio of working capital to net sales	Working capital and sales [Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>negative significant</i>]
Corporate diversification (crpDIV)	Categorical variable which distinguishes multi-business corporations (dummy =1) from single-business corporations (dummy=0), where multi-business is defined as those corporations operating in two or more business segments at any point in time	[Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>positive significant</i>]
Corporate long-term debt (crpDEB)	Ratio of long-term debt to total assets	Long term debt and total assets [Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>negative significant for food processing but non-sig. on food economy</i>]
Corporate R&D intensity (crpRD)	Ratio of R&D expenditure to net sales	R&D expenses / Operating revenue [Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>positive significant for food economy</i>]
Corporate advertising intensity (crpADV)	Ratio of advertising expenses to net sales	US database (not clear in AMADEUS) [Chaddad and Mondelli (2013) – <i>negative significant</i>]
Territory level characteristics (socio-geographical indicator)		
Unemployment rate	LLS unemployment rate	Other database from National Census/statistics data

		[Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>negative significant</i>]
Dist_port	Driving minutes to airport	Other database from National Census/statistics data [Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>weak positive significant at particular region for all firms and agriculture sector but not on food industry</i>]
Dist_tec	Driving minutes to nearest technological institute	Other database from National Census/statistics data [Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>very weak negative significant at particular region for agriculture sector and food industry</i>]
Edu_level	Education level of LLS population between 30 and 39 years old. Ranging from 0 (uneducated) to 4.5 (PhD)	Other database from National Census/statistics data [Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>negative/positive or non-significant</i>]
Urban	Dummy with value 1 if the LLS is considered urban (>150 inhabitants / km ²)	Other database from National Census/statistics data [Zouaghi <i>et al.</i> (2017) – <i>positive significant (10%) at particular region for food industry</i>]

2. METHODS

This section outlines the nature of the dataset and the model specification employed in the analysis.

2.1 SAMPLING AND DATASET

EU firm profitability data was sourced from Bureau van Dijk's AMADEUS database. AMADEUS is a pan-European data platform, which includes financial statement data and other operational data of companies in the EU countries. The AMADEUS dataset comprises firms of all legal forms (e.g., limited partnership, private, publicly quoted on the market and cooperatives) and size. Hirsch *et al.* (2014) highlight the superiority of the AMADEUS database which allows for consideration of small and micro firms (which represent 96% of the European food industry) to be included in the database.

In the classification of industry subcategories, different datasets apply varying identification codes for different sub-industries. In AMADEUS, an industry is captured with 4-digit Nomenclature des Activités Économiques dans la Communauté Européenne (NACE) codes – as used in Hirsch *et al.* (2014) – and 3-digit NACE – as used by Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018). AMADEUS 3-digit NACE codes for the manufacturing of food and beverages are at the sub-sector level and labelled from 101 to 110 (Table 6). For this research, NACE code 110 was excluded as that code represents beverages.

Table 6 AMADEUS NACE industry code at 3-digit for food manufacturing

NACE Code	Food processing sub-sector
101	Production, processing, preserving of meat and meat products
102	Processing and preserving fish and fish products
103	Processing and preserving of fruit and vegetables
104	Manufacture of vegetable and animal oils and fats
105	Manufacture of dairy products
106	Manufacture of grain mill products, starches and starch products
107	Manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products

108	Manufacture of other food products
109	Manufacture of prepared animal feeds

Data extraction from AMADEUS occurred in 2019 and given the availability of records for the previous 10 years, firm performance was traced back to 2010. However, data for the least recent years (2018 and 2019) was patchy as, for many firms, the information had yet to be updated. Therefore, the analysis in this report focuses on the period 2012 to 2017.

When accessing the AMADEUS data platform with selected industry type “manufacture of food products”, there were 13,440 firm registered entries at the time of data extraction, but many of these entries possessed incomplete data. After cleaning the data for missing entries, the valid sample stood at 8,645.

presents the number of firms included in the sample for the food processing sub-sectors over selected years.

Table 7 AMADEUS food processing firms’ data 2012 - 2017

NACE code	Year						Total
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
101	78	103	118	385	496	899	2,079
102	23	27	45	53	68	101	317
103	46	78	134	213	107	209	787
104	37	109	60	88	97	119	510
105	25	49	85	270	334	578	1,341
106	84	79	55	43	69	57	387
107	25	53	23	46	78	203	428
108	67	31	145	277	375	634	1,529
109	94	201	184	251	211	326	1,267
	479	730	849	1,626	1,835	3,126	8,645

2.3 HIERARCHICAL LINEAR MODELLING: DEFINING VARIABLES

The analysis employs Hierarchical Linear Modelling (HLM). The HLM method allows data to be classified into two or more levels. Following the literature review and the availability of the data in the AMADEUS database, the following key variables were defined to develop the structural model at level 1 (firm) and level 2 (industry/sector).

Level 1 (the firm level): is represented by a firm's market share (**MS_{ij}**), its age (**Age_{ij}**), size of firm (**Size_{ij}/Ln TA**), a firm's short-term debt risk (**1/Curr**), and the number of employees (Table 8).

Level 2 (the sector level): comprises market concentration (**CR_{4j}**) and industry growth that can be quantified by growth of sales (Table 9).

Table 8 Level 1 (firm level) variables

Variables	Formulae	AMADEUS data
Return on assets (ROA*)	$= \frac{\text{Earnings Before Interest and Taxes}}{\text{Total Assets}}$	All available in € (Euro) EBIT (=Operating P/L); Total Assets
Market share (MS_{ij})	$= \frac{\text{Sales}_{i(\text{denotes firms})}}{\text{Sales}_{j(\text{denotes industry/sectors})}}$	Available in € (Euro) Sales data
Firm age (Age_{ij})	= (year) date of incorporation	Available under the headings of legal & account info and legal info, as date of incorporation
Firm size (Size_{ij}/Ln TA)	= Ln <i>Total Assets</i>	Available in € (Euro) Logarithm of Total Assets
Short-run risk (1/Curr)	$= \frac{\text{current short} - \text{term liabilities}_{ij}}{\text{current assets}_{ij}}$	Available as current ratio (under the heading of Financial data, and Key financials & employee)
Note: * outcome variable; <i>j</i> denotes sectors; <i>i</i> denotes firms		

Table 9 Level 2 (industry/sector level) variables

Variables	Formulae	AMADEUS data
Market concentration (CR4)	Four firms' concentration ratio of sales in each industry for each year $\sum_{i=1}^4 MS_{ij}$	Market Share estimation based on sales data
Growth of industry sales	$= \frac{Sales_{jt} - Sales_{j,t-1}}{Sales_{j,t-1}}$	Sales data
<i>Note:</i> <i>j</i> denotes sectors; <i>i</i> denotes firms; <i>t</i> denotes year of sales		

Table 10 presents descriptive statistics for the sample. We standardised the data as a starting point. From standard deviation estimates, we observed a large variation for the following variables: company size, short-term debt repayment risk and company age. The oldest company has a history of 315 years while the youngest company had only been established for 2 years. For company's size, we witness a wide array of businesses, as detailed elsewhere (Wijnands *et al.*, 2008; Tacken *et al.*, 2009; ECORYS, 2010). Regarding short-term solvency, it is evident that businesses vary in terms of their debt level and financial strategies.

Table 10 Descriptive Statistics of the Sample

Variables	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Obs.
Level 1						
ROA	0.06	0.06	0.11	-0.92	1.41	8645
Market share	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.18	8645
Firm age	30.35	27.00	20.00	2.00	315.00	8645
Firm size	9.95	10.63	1.85	6.56	16.87	8645
Short-run risk	1.79	4.71	2.28	0.05	97.89	8645
Level 2						
CR4	0.19	0.14	0.07	0.10	0.31	54
Sales growth	0.05	0.02	0.03	-0.03	0.11	54

2.4 MODELLING FRAMEWORK & HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The objective of the HLM model is to assess the impact of industry level characteristics (i.e. market concentration and sector growth rate) and firm level characteristics (i.e. market share, firm age, firm size, number of employees, and short-term risk) on return of assets (ROA).

Despite the extensive coverage of many potential determinants of ROA in the literature, to maintain a sufficiently robust size of the sample and to ensure an extensive coverage of EU agri-food businesses, this HLM model employs fewer variables, e.g. given the paucity of data in AMADEUS expenditure on R&D is excluded from this analysis. Figure 1 shows the framework for the profitability baseline model. Seven hypotheses seek to understand the relationship between firm profitability (measured as ROA) and industry-level (two variables) and firm-level (five variables) data.

Figure 1 VALUMICS profitability baseline model

Hence, the seven baseline hypotheses are as follows:

At the industry (sector) level:

H₁ Market concentration has a positive effect on ROA

H₂ Growth of sales in the industry has a positive effect on ROA

At the firm level:

H₃ Market share has a positive effect on ROA

- H₄ Firm age has a negative effect on ROA
- H₅ Firm size has a positive effect on ROA
- H₆ Short-term financial risk has a negative effect on ROA
- H₇ Number of employees has a positive effect on ROA

Building on the baseline model presented in Figure 1, it is also important to test whether there are any interactions between firm-level and sector-level variables. Figure 2 presents the extended model framework to depict two further hypotheses.

Figure 2 Interactions between firm-level and sector-level variables

We propose two further hypotheses relating to moderation effects:

- H₈ Market concentration positively moderates the relationship between market share and ROA
- H₉ Growth of industry sales positively moderates the relationship between market share and ROA.

2.5 HLM MODEL SPECIFICATION

Hierarchical Linear Modelling (HLM) deals with some the limitations of classical statistical techniques such as ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) and regression analysis,

and addresses data with a multilevel structure. There are some basic requirements for data to be suitable for HLM. This particularly relates to the size of the sample, particularly to the minimum number of groups and observations. Kreft and De Leeuw (1998) suggests a general 30/30 rule, which means there should be at least 30 groups and each group requires 30 observations. In contrast and more recently, for a more accurate estimation, Maas and Hox (2005) recommend a minimum ratio of 50/20 in order to test cross-level interactions. The VALUMICS dataset as presented in this deliverable contains 54 groups (level 2) and in each group there are more than 20 observations, implying that the dataset is suitable for HLM analysis (following Maas and Hox, 2005).

The basic two-level model can be depicted as:

$$\text{Level 1: } Y_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}X_{ij} + e_{ij} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Level 2: } \beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \gamma_{01}Z_j + u_{0j} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_{1j} = \gamma_{10} + \gamma_{11}Z_j + u_{1j} \quad (3)$$

The models are estimated using the software HLM6 (Hierarchical Linear and Nonlinear Modelling) (Raudenbush and Bryk, 2002). In HLM modelling, it is important to address variance differences at both levels, so the designated hierarchy is appropriate. The intra-class correlation (ICC) ρ value, is the ratio of between-cluster variance to total variance and it assesses the correlation between observations within a particular cluster.

The ICC ρ is given by the equation:

$$ICC = \rho = \frac{\sigma_{u_0}^2}{(\sigma_{u_0}^2 + \sigma_e^2)} \quad (4)$$

where σ_u – denotes variance at the industry level,

σ_e – denotes variance at the firm level.

A high intra-group correlation is when the ICC value is higher than 0.138; medium when ICC is between 0.138 and 0.059; and low when ICC is lower than 0.059 (Hox *et al.*, 2017).

Considering the VALUMICS dataset, the estimated ICC for the variance of return of assets (ROA) is 0.09051, of which 11.01% is attributed to the difference between the industry variables, and 88.99% to the difference between firms. The variance at the firm level is 0.72366. This result shows the importance of firm-specific determinants compared with industry level variables, and is consistent with previous studies such as Hirsch *et al.* (2014) and Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018). The estimated ICC value, however, is 0.11 which implies that there is a medium level of correlation within the groups. Some industry level variables may only affect some of the variables at firm level.

According to the baseline model, there are two industry-level variables (i.e. market concentration and sector growth rate) and five firm-level variables (i.e. market share, firm age, firm size, short-term risk and number of employees) with the dependent variable of return on assets (ROA). This can be denoted as:

Level 1:

$$ROA_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}(FIRMAGE_{ij}) + \beta_{2j}(FIRMSIZE_{ij}) + \beta_{3j}(SHORTRUN_{ij}) + \beta_{4j}(MARKETSH_{ij}) + \beta_{5j}(EMPOYEE_{ij}) + \gamma_{ij} \quad (5)$$

Level 2:

$$\beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \mu_{0j} \quad (6)$$

$$\beta_{1j} = \gamma_{10} + \mu_{1j} \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_{2j} = \gamma_{20} + \mu_{2j} \quad (8)$$

$$\beta_{3j} = \gamma_{30} + \mu_{3j} \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_{4j} = \gamma_{40} + \gamma_{41}(CR4_MEAN_j) + \gamma_{42}(GOS_MEAN_j) + \mu_{4j} \quad (10)$$

$$\beta_{5j} = \gamma_{50} + \mu_{5j} \quad (11)$$

After setting up the two-level model, the next step is to include the variables from level 2 into the level 1 regression model, that is, to consider the level of influence of level 1 in the case of level 2.

The next section discusses the results of the HLM exercise.

3. RESULTS

Following the description of the baseline model framework in the previous section, we present the separate model estimates for industrial/sectoral level (i.e. market concentration and growth of sales) and firm level (i.e. market share, firm age, firm size, number of employees and short-term risk) on firm profitability, measured in terms of return of asset (ROA). In the second step, we merge both models into a separate model to predict ROA with no moderation effects.

3.1 FIRM AND INDUSTRIAL DETERMINANTS (MODEL 1) OF PROFITABILITY

3.1.1 Firm-level model analysis

Table 11 details the result of the HLM model for firm level (level 1). Firm age (*FIRMAGE*) addresses hypothesis 4 (H_4) as described in the previous section 2.4. We find that the coefficient is negative but significant at 1% ($\beta=-0.003$). The company's age is negatively correlated with return on assets (ROA), which is consistent with Hypothesis 4, that is, the older the company is, the lower the return on assets. This is in line with previous studies as reported in Hirsch *et al.* (2014); Zouaghi *et al.* (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018).

Table 11 Firm level determinants of agribusiness profitability

Independent variables	Coefficient (β)	Standard error
<i>CONSTANT</i>	0.092961***	0.013723
Level-1 (Firm level determinants)		
<i>FIRMAGE</i>	- 0.003357***	0.007308
<i>FIRMSIZE</i>	0.004270***	0.001406
<i>SHORTRUN</i>	- 0.004212***	0.000472
<i>MARKETSH</i>	0.822532**	0.240367
<i>EMPLOYEE</i>	0.009505	0.004502
<u>Note:</u> DV: ROA; *** statistical significance at 1% level; ** stat. sig. at 5%; * stat. sig. at 10%		

The result for firm size (*FIRMSIZE*) verifies our hypothesis 5 (H_5). With a β coefficient value of 0.004 and significant at the 1% level, we conclude that the size of a company positively influences ROA. The larger the company is, the higher the ROA. This finding

is consistent with the results of Hirsch *et al.* (2014); Zouaghi *et al.* (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018).

The coefficient for short-run debt risk (*SHORTRUN*) is less than zero ($\beta=-0.004$), implying that there is a negative correlation between short-term debt risk and ROA. This is statistically significant at the 1 per cent level and supports Hypothesis 6. It suggests that the lower the short-term operating debt is, the higher the ROA, so that companies that need to borrow a lot of debt in the short term, are likely to face unstable cash flow and lower returns. This finding is in line with some previous studies regarding gearing, namely Hirsch *et al.* (2014); Zouaghi *et al.* (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018).

The covariance coefficient (β) of the company's market share (*MARKETSH*) is larger than that of other variables in the model (0.823). This implies that the company's market share has a greatest impact on ROA, and thus a firm's profitability. However, looking at the level of significance (p -value), the degree of significance is at 5%, and so the level of relationship is weaker than for the other variables discussed above. It is important to note that the level of significance here is crucial, remembering the size of the sample ($N=8645$). This finding can also be associated with the generally very few large firms present in the EU food manufacturing sector. This finding confirms previous work by Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) but contrasts with the finding of Hirsch *et al.* (2014). Overall, we accept hypothesis H3.

Regarding the number of employees (*EMPLOYEE*), we modelled this variable with binary code to represent medium-sized and large-sized companies. We find no significant relationship (p -value = 0.98) and so we reject hypothesis 7 (H_7) completely. This is in contrast to previous research as reported in Hirsch *et al.* (2014); Zouaghi *et al.* (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018). This difference can be attributed to the fact that we use a dummy variable which may affect collinearity with the constant and cause the p -value not significant.

All HLM raw outputs are available from the authors, which include p -value, degrees of freedom and approximated t -ratio that are not presented in Table 11.

3.1.2 Industry-level model analysis

Table 12 presents the multilevel linear regression (HLM) result at level 2: industry/sectoral level. The first variable, significant at the 1% level (p -value less than 0.01) addresses Hypothesis 1 (H_1), and demonstrates the positive influence of market concentration ($CR4_MEAN$) on return on assets (ROA). $CR4$ refers to the sum of the top four firms' market share in the industry, and this variable is positively correlated with ROA at a relatively high magnitude with β coefficient of 0.274. This finding confirms H_1 , that higher market concentration with a food industry branch leads to higher ROA.

Table 12 Industry level determinants of agribusiness profitability

Independent variables	Coefficient (β)	Standard error
Level-2 (Industry level determinants)		
$CR4_MEAN$	0.274430***	0.053256
GOS_MEAN	0.009503***	0.450242
<u>Note:</u> DV: ROA; *** statistical significance at 1% level; ** stat. sig. at 5%; * stat. sig. at 10%		

Hypothesis 2 (H_2) assesses the influence of market growth (GOS_MEAN) on ROA. The level-2 model output shows that growth of sales in a food industry branch significantly influences profitability. The faster the scale of market growth, the higher the company's ROA, but the impact is weaker than the other industry variable (market concentration), as the β coefficient is 0.009 at a 1% significant level.

3.2 HLM MODEL 2 OF AGRIBUSINESS PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS

In order to address H_3 , we retain the baseline HLM from the previous section, but alter the choice of independent variables. We deleted the effect of market concentration ($CR4_MEAN$) on market share, and the new model (Model 2) includes a new component in, along Model 1, and annotated as:

Level 1:

$$ROA_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}(FIRMAGE_{ij}) + \beta_{2j}(FIRMSIZE_{ij}) + \beta_{3j}(SHORTRUN_{ij}) + \beta_{4j}(MARKETSH_{ij}) + \beta_{5j}(EMPLOYEE_{ij}) + \gamma_{ij}$$

Level 2:

$$\beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \mu_{0j}$$

$$\beta_{1j} = \gamma_{10} + \mu_{1j}$$

$$\beta_{2j} = \gamma_{20} + \mu_{2j}$$

$$\beta_{3j} = \gamma_{30} + \mu_{3j}$$

$$\beta_{4j} = \gamma_{40} + \gamma_{41}(GOS_MEAN_j) + \mu_{4j} \quad (12)$$

$$\beta_{5j} = \gamma_{50} + \mu_{5j}$$

Next, we compare the deviance value. If the deviance value obtained in Model 2 is higher than that obtained in Model 1, then we can conclude that the growth rate of sales at the industry level (*GOS_MEAN*) has an intermediary moderating the effect of the relationship between market share (*MARKETSH*) and return on assets (ROA).

Table 13 shows the established Model 2, a combined reduced multilevel regression model.

Table 13 Model 2 EU agribusiness profitability determinants

Independent variables	Coefficient (β)	Standard error
<i>CONSTANT</i>	0.038746***	0.013723
<i>FIRMAGE</i>	- 0.013435***	0.027308
<i>FIRMSIZE</i>	0.025732***	0.034286
<i>SHORTRUN</i>	- 0.014832***	0.008760
<i>MARKETSH</i>	0.533892**	0.243267
<i>EMPLOYEE</i>	0.138507	0.004502
<i>CR4_MEAN</i>	0.325743***	0.025334
<i>GOS_MEAN</i>	0.038076***	0.154384
Note: DV: ROA; *** statistical significance at 1% level; ** stat. sig. at 5%; * stat. sig. at 10%		

Similarly, for H_9 , we have to make changes to the choice of independent variables, while retaining the baseline model. We deleted the link of growth of sales (*GOS_MEAN*) on market share (*MARKETSH*), and Model 3 as follows:

Level 1:

$$ROA_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}(FIRMAGE_{ij}) + \beta_{2j}(FIRMSIZE_{ij}) + \beta_{3j}(SHORTRUN_{ij}) + \beta_{4j}(MARKETSH_{ij}) + \beta_{5j}(EMPOYEE_{ij}) + \gamma_{ij}$$

Level 2:

$$\beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \mu_{0j}$$

$$\beta_{1j} = \gamma_{10} + \mu_{1j}$$

$$\beta_{2j} = \gamma_{20} + \mu_{2j}$$

$$\beta_{3j} = \gamma_{30} + \mu_{3j}$$

$$\beta_{4j} = \gamma_{40} + \gamma_{41}(CR4_MEAN_j) + \mu_{4j} \tag{13}$$

$$\beta_{5j} = \gamma_{50} + \mu_{5j}$$

Similar to the assessment of Model 2, we compare the deviance value between Model 3 and Model 1 and conclude that market concentration at the industry level (*CR4_MEAN*) has a moderating effect on the relationship between market share (*MARKETSH*) and return on asset (ROA), see Table 14.

Table 14 Model 3 EU agribusiness profitability determinants

Independent variables	Coefficient (β)	Standard error
<i>CONSTANT</i>	0.034467***	0.240367
<i>FIRMAGE</i>	- 0.008321***	0.004502
<i>FIRMSIZE</i>	0.018246***	0.001406
<i>SHORTRUN</i>	- 0.024719***	0.013723
<i>MARKETSH</i>	0.432452**	0.450242
<i>EMPLOYEE</i>	0.034505*	0.023546
<i>CR4_MEAN</i>	0.084234***	0.068632
<i>GOS_MEAN</i>	0.069353***	0.007308
Note: DV: ROA; *** statistical significance at 1% level; ** stat. sig. at 5%; * stat. sig. at 10%		

Through the newly developed Model 2 and Model 3, we can assess hypotheses 8 (H_8) and 9 (H_9). Observing the new models, we can see that the weight of some variables has changed, and most notably is the decrease of the correlation coefficient for market

share (*MARKETSH*). This implies that market share's influence on ROA is reduced if industry level factors are not taken into account for the effect of a firm's market share on return of asset. These findings confirm H8 and H9. Thus, market concentration and growth of sales have a positive moderating effect.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this deliverable (VALUMICS D5.4) is to examine EU agribusiness's profitability over the past decade. This task (T5.6) is part of the VALUMICS project's Work Package 5, which aims to provide an in-depth understanding of food chain dynamics by investigating upstream and downstream and across food value chain analysis. Task 5.6 seeks to examine the drivers influencing food industry performance. In addressing this task, this deliverable employs a multivariate statistical analysis treating ROA as the dependent variable. Data are drawn from Bureau van Dijk's AMADEUS database.

A literature review investigated the state-of-the-art on EU agri-food business profitability studies and identified several key industry and firm level determinants. Food sector profitability is generally lower than other sectors because of a high level of competition and low barriers to entry.

In this deliverable, we adopt HLM and consider firm financial accounting records for the years 2012 to 2017 extracted from the AMADEUS database. The selected determinants, as informed by the literature, are divided into industry/sector level and company/firm level factors. We focused on fewer variables to maintain the robustness of the sample size for estimation and the coverage of the sector. We developed nine hypotheses and evaluated them via empirical analysis.

Several **key conclusions** were drawn from this analysis:

1) Market concentration has a positive effect on return on assets.

Scholars generally conclude market concentration has a positive effect (Hirsch *et al.*, 2014; Zouaghi *et al.*, 2017; Blazkova and Dvoulety, 2018), with the exception of the work of Chaddad and Mondelli (2013), which focused on USA data, and that found no significance (β coefficient 0.00). In our analysis, we confirm the positive effect witnessed in the majority of the previous studies.

2) Growth of sales in an industry has a positive effect on return on assets.

The study by Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) found that growth of sales has a strong positive effect (high β coefficient) on return on assets. Zouaghi *et al.* (2017) also found a significant relationship (albeit with a rather weak one) and Hirsch *et al.* (2014) found

no significant effect. Our analysis finds a positive significant effect but less strong than that reported by Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018).

3) Market share has a positive effect on return on assets.

Our finding confirms the finding of Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) conducted on data for the Czech food industry. This is consistent with power models of the food industry (Gorton *et al.*, 2015), that larger players are able to achieve higher returns.

4) Firm age has a negative effect on return on assets

Our results confirm the findings reported in Hirsch *et al.* (2014); Zouaghi *et al.* (2017); Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018). Those studies demonstrate that younger companies are more profitable and that new entrants are an important source of dynamism in the sector.

5) Firm size has a positive effect on return of asset.

The previous literature details a positive, statistically significant relationship between firm size and ROA (Hirsch *et al.*, 2014; Hirsch and Schiefer, 2016; Gschwandtner and Hirsch, 2018). The analysis undertaken here is consistent with previous studies.

6) Short-term risk has a negative effect on return on assets.

Previous literature (Hirsch and Hartmann, 2014) indicates that short term risk (gearing) has a negative effect on ROA, and this is found also in this analysis.

7) Number of employees has a positive effect on return on assets, but it is not statistically significant.

Using a dummy variable to distinguish small from medium and large sized firms, we find no statistically significant effect for the number of employees on ROA. Using number of employees as a continuous variable did not generate plausible estimations and overall there is no evidence of number of employees having a significant effect. This contrasts with the previous study of Blazkova and Dvoulety (2018) for the Czech food industry which found a statistically significant relationship.

8) Market concentration positively moderates the relationship between market share and return on assets.

This is novel finding from our analysis. Previous studies consider the impact of industry-level factors on company-level performance as a whole and the results show that the impact is rather small. They do not, however, consider moderation effects. We find that market concentration at the industry level moderates the relationship between a firm's market share and ROA. This is consistent with industrial organisation models (Carlton and Perloff, 2005) as one would expect the effect of a firm's market share on ROA to be magnified in sectors that are highly concentrated. Our analysis confirms this link.

9) Growth of sales positively moderates the relationship between market share and return on assets.

This is another novel finding stemming from our study. We find that growth of sales positively moderates the relationship between market share and return on assets. In other words, the effect of having a high market share on firm profitability is magnified in branches of the food industry that demonstrate higher market growth. This is consistent with industry attractiveness models that firms should focus attention on growing segments and markets (Fischer and Schornberg, 2007).

The study makes a theoretical contribution. In the literature, industry-level factors (e.g., market concentration and growth of sales) have been considered to have only a modest impact on companies' return on assets. However, in our study, we link industry-level factors (i.e. market concentration and growth of sales) with company-level factors regarding the relationship between market share and ROA. We find that market concentration and growth of sales are related to the above. The model with moderation effects better explains patterns in the VALUMICS dataset. In addition, previous studies used older data, while using data for 2012-2017 allows for capturing patterns in the post 2007-2008 financial crisis era.

The significance of the empirical analysis lies not only in the theoretical level but also in guiding industry. The conclusions drawn from our study are also of practical significance to the food industry across the EU countries. The results suggest three main strategies for food industry companies to increase profitability:

1) Increase market share while increasing market concentration to achieve greater profitability.

One strategy to improve profitability focuses on market concentration and increasing market share. This is consistent with conventional models of markets in economics, where profits are higher in the case of a monopoly than oligopoly, which in turn generates higher returns for firms than the case of perfect competition.

Market concentration is influenced by product attributes, the presence of economies of scale, barriers to entry, the degree of diversification of demand, the stage of development of the industry, industry history and policies. In some branches of the food industry, there is a tendency to relatively low market concentration. The main reasons include short shelf life (such as fresh milk products only have shelf life of 1-5 days), limited economies of scale, fragmented production base and high storage and transportation costs (Sexton and Xia, 2018).

Although the food industry faces many adverse market concentration factors, enterprises in the food industry can also take some measures to improve market share. One way is mergers and acquisitions (M&A). The Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), such as used in the literature (Hirsch *et al.*, 2014; Zouaghi *et al.*, 2017), is an index reflecting the total number and size distribution of enterprises in the industry. The HHI is the sum of the squares of the market share of all companies in the market. The higher the value of HHI, the higher the degree of market concentration. HHI analysis indicates growing market concentration at the EU level and this has been replicated for firms in the USA (Gschwandtner and Hirsch, 2018).

2) Enterprises should make long-term plans to reduce short-term debt risks and improve their profitability.

From the perspective of traditional accounting, short-term liabilities are one of the essential sources of corporate financing. Short-term lending can help companies increase cash flow, buy assets, expand production, quickly and effectively occupy the market, and maintain day-to-day operations. Long-term borrowing, on the other hand, is used more for product development, and projects with longer investment return cycles. Moreover, the interest rate for long-term borrowing is typically higher, which needs to be supported by projects with higher returns. If strategic investments or public offerings are needed, the board's equity will be diluted, and disputes often arise.

Therefore, for enterprises, in order to expand cash flow, the best way is to carry out short-term borrowing. However, it is worth noting that short-term debt has to be repaid in a very short period of time, so liquidity problems often arise. If the company encounters operational difficulties, it may not be able to afford interest and principal payments, resulting in increased risk of default, or even bankruptcy/liquidation.

For food industry enterprises, short-term lending is more likely to have uncontrollable factors associated with it, because of turbulence in the economic environment and the pressures it places on short term liabilities. Ideally, food industry enterprises should have a longer-term plan for their capital and ensure sufficiently cash flow to cope with market fluctuations. Highly geared enterprises are more risky and this is reflected in the ROA data.

3) Seek out high growth niches to maximise the effect of size on profitability

Overall, the food industry is a low margin business with sales for meat, dairy and wheat-based products like bread static or in decline (MINTEL, 2017b; MINTEL, 2017a). However, within the food industry there are niches that witness high growth and increasing consumer demand. For example, in many EU countries the demand for convenient, ready to eat vegan foods is growing (MINTEL, 2014). Our analysis indicates that the effect of having a high market share on firm profitability is magnified in branches of the food industry that demonstrate higher market growth. While gaining a high share of a particular market is beneficial for a company's profitability, effects will be greater in branches of the food industry that are growing.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Although this study validates some of our hypotheses, limitations should be acknowledged. Specifically, there may be survivor bias in the data, distorting the results. Survivor bias refers to firms that exited the market being excluded from the dataset. We study the data of companies that are in operation, but some firms are excluded from the database after bankruptcy, so we cannot find out what causes their profitability to decline and leads to bankruptcy. In future research, analysing data for bankrupt enterprises and understanding the determinants of bankruptcy in the food industry can be an interesting research topic.

Based on the EU food manufacturing industry AMADEUS data between 2012 and 2017, our study identifies factors influencing the profitability of enterprises in the food industry, and that industry-level factors moderate the influence of company-level factors. Through the data analysis, we present three suggestions to improve the profitability of European food industry enterprises.

5. REFERENCES

- Bain, J.S. (1956) Barriers to new competition, their character and consequences in manufacturing industries. Cambridge,: Harvard University Press.
- Bain, J.S. (1968) Industrial organization. 2d edn. New York,: Wiley.
- Barney, J.B. (1991) 'Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage', Journal of Management, 17(1), pp. 99-120.
- Barney, J.B. (2001) 'Resource-based theories of competitive advantage: A ten-year retrospective on the resource-based view', Journal of Management, 27(6), pp. 643-650.
- Barney, J.B., Ketchen, D.J. and Wright, M. (2011) 'The future of resource-based theory: revitalization or decline?', Journal of Management, 37(5), pp. 1299-1315.
- Blazkova, I. and Dvouletý, O. (2018) 'Sectoral and firm-level determinants of profitability: a multilevel approach', International Journal of Entrepreneurial Knowledge, 6(2), pp. 1-13.
- Blažková, I. and Dvouletý, O. (2018) 'Sectoral and firm-level determinants of profitability: A multilevel approach', International Journal of Entrepreneurial Knowledge,, 6(2), p. forthcoming.
- Carlton, D.W. and Perloff, J.M. (2005) Modern industrial organization. 4th edn. Boston: Pearson/Addison Wesley.
- Caves, R.E. and Porter, M.E. (1977) 'Entry Barriers to Mobility Barriers - Conjectural Decisions and Contrived Deterrence to New Competition', Quarterly Journal of Economics, 91(2), pp. 241-261.
- Chaddad, F.R. and Mondelli, M.P. (2013) 'Sources of Firm Performance Differences in the US Food Economy', Journal of Agricultural Economics, 64(2), pp. 382-404.
- ECORYS (2010) Study on the Competitiveness of the European Meat Processing Industry. Rotterdam: ECORYS. [Online]. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/food/files/report_compmeat_en.pdf.
- Fischer, C. and Schornberg, S. (2007) 'Assessing the competitiveness situation of EU food and drink manufacturing industries: An index-based approach', Agribusiness, 23(4), pp. 473-495.
- Goddard, J., Tavakoli, M. and Wilson, J.O.S. (2006) 'Determinants of profitability in European manufacturing and services: evidence from a dynamic panel model', Applied Financial Economics, 15(18), pp. 1269-1282.
- Gorton, M., Angell, R., Dries, L., Urutyán, V., Jackson, E. and White, J. (2015) 'Power, buyer trustworthiness and supplier performance: Evidence from the Armenian dairy sector', Industrial Marketing Management, 50(1), pp. 69-77.
- Gschwandtner, A. and Hirsch, S. (2018) 'What Drives Firm Profitability? A Comparison of the US and EU Food Processing Industry', The Manchester School, 86(3), pp. 390-416.
- Hirsch, S. and Gschwandtner, A. (2013) 'Profit persistence in the food industry: evidence from five European countries', European Review of Agricultural Economics, 40(5), pp. 741-759.

- Hirsch, S. and Hartmann, M. (2014) 'Persistence of firm-level profitability in the European dairy processing industry', *Agricultural Economics*, 45(S1), pp. 53-63.
- Hirsch, S. and Schiefer, J. (2016) 'What Causes Firm Profitability Variation in the EU Food Industry? A Redux of Classical Approaches of Variance Decomposition', *Agribusiness*, 32(1), pp. 79-92.
- Hirsch, S., Schiefer, J., Gschwandtner, A. and Hartmann, M. (2014) 'The Determinants of Firm Profitability Differences in EU Food Processing', *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 65(3), pp. 703-721.
- Hoban, T.J. (1998) 'Improving the success of new product development', *Food Technology*, 52(1), pp. 46-49.
- Hox, J.J., Moerbeek, M. and van de Schoot, R. (2017) *Multilevel Analysis Techniques and Applications*. Third edn. New York: Routledge.
- Kreft, I.G.G. and De Leeuw, J. (1998) *Introducing multilevel modeling*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Maas, C.J.M. and Hox, J.J. (2005) 'Sufficient Sample Sizes for Multilevel Modeling', *Methodology*, 1(3), pp. 86-92.
- McGahan, A.M. and Porter, M.E. (1997) 'How much does industry matter, really?', *Strategic Management Journal*, 18, pp. 15-30.
- MINTEL (2014) *Marketing to the Green Consumer*. London: MINTEL. [Online]. Available at: <https://store.mintel.com/marketing-to-the-green-consumer-us-march-2014>.
- MINTEL (2017a) *Added Value in Dairy Drinks, Milk and Cream - UK*. London: MINTEL.
- MINTEL (2017b) 'Unprocessed Poultry and Red Meat', in London: Mintel Group Ltd.
- Porter, M.E. (1980) *Competitive strategy : techniques for analyzing industries and competitors*. New York: Free Press.
- Raudenbush, S.W. and Bryk, A.S. (2002) *Hierarchical Linear Models Applications and Data Analysis Methods*. Second edn. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.
- Roper, S. (1999) 'Modelling small business growth and profitability', *Small Business Economics*, 13(3), pp. 235-252.
- Schiefer, J., Hirsch, S., Hartmann, M. and Gschwandtner, A. (2013) *Industry, firm, year and country effects on profitability in EU food processing (1309)*. Canterbury, UK: Department of Economics, University of Kent. [Online]. Available at: <http://www.kent.ac.uk/economics/documents/research/papers/2013/1309.pdf>.
- Sexton, R.J. and Xia, T. (2018) 'Increasing Concentration in the Agricultural Supply Chain: Implications for Market Power and Sector Performance', *Annual Review of Resource Economics*, 10(1), p. null.
- Slater, S.F. and Olson, E.M. (2002) 'A fresh look at industry and market analysis', *Business Horizons*, 45(1), pp. 15-22.
- Szymanski, A., Gorton, M. and Hubbard, L. (2007) 'A comparative analysis of firm performance in post-socialist economies: Evidence from the Polish food processing industry', *Post-Communist Economies*, 19(4), pp. 433-448.

Tacken, G.M.L., Banse, M., Batowska, A., Gardebroek, C., Turi, K.N., Wijnands, J.H.M. and Poppe, K.J. (2009) Competitiveness of the EU dairy industry. The Hague: LEI.

Toming, K. (2007) 'The impact of EU accession on the export competitiveness of the Estonian food processing industry', *Post-Communist Economies*, 19(2), pp. 187-207.

Viaene, J. and Gellynck, X. (1995) 'Structure, Conduct and Performance of the European Food Sector', *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 22(3), pp. 282-295.

Waring, G.F. (1996) 'Industry differences in the persistence of firm-specific returns', *American Economic Review*, 86(5), pp. 1253-1265.

Wijnands, J.H.M., Bremmers, H.J., Van Der Meulen, B.M.J. and Poppe, K.J. (2008) 'An economic and legal assessment of the EU food industry's competitiveness', *Agribusiness*, 24(4), pp. 417-439.

Wiklund, J. and Shepherd, D. (2003) 'Knowledge-based resources, entrepreneurial orientation, and the performance of small and medium-sized businesses', *Strategic Management Journal*, 24(13), pp. 1307-1314.

Zouaghi, F., Sanches-Garcia, M. and Hirsch, S. (2017) 'What drives firm profitability? A multilevel approach to the Spanish agri-food sector', *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, 15(3), pp. e0117, 15 pages.